

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Benzyl Alcohol by Tetraethylammonium Chlorochromate : A New Chromium(VI) Oxidant

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There has been a continued interest in the development of new chromium(vi) reagents for the effective oxidation of organic substrates, particularly alcohols, under mild conditions¹. Herein we introduce a new reagent, tetraethylammonium chlorochromate (TEACC), and kinetics of oxidation of benzyl alcohol by this reagent in dimethylformamide was undertaken.

Results and Discussion

The oxidation of benzyl alcohol (BA) by TEACC, in dimethylformamide gives benzaldehyde in high yield (>80%). Under the present experimental conditions, there was no further oxidation of benzaldehyde. Excess of TEACC was allowed to react and the unreacted chromium(vi) estimated. In some runs, however, an excess of alcohol was used followed by the estimation of the carbonyl product as its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. The stoichiometry of the reaction can be represented as

The oxidation of benzyl alcohol by TEACC is first order with respect to TEACC. Further the pseudo-first-order rate coefficients obtained from the linear plots of $\log [\text{TEACC}]$ vs time are independent of the initial concentration of TEACC (Table 1). The rate increases with an increase in the concentration of the alcohol but the order is one (Table 1). A plot of $1/k_1$ vs $1/[\text{BA}]$ is linear with an intercept on the rate ordinate. This might imply that a Michaelis-Menten type kinetics is followed with respect to the alcohol, and a broad mechanism may be postulated as

The reaction was catalysed by acid, and showed a first order dependence on acidity (Table 1). The acid-catalysed oxidation of benzyl alcohol was studied in solutions containing varying proportions of DMF-H₂O. It is seen (Table

TABLE I

Dependence of the reaction rate on oxidant concentration

[BA] = 0.20 mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄] = 0.10 mol dm⁻³, Temp = 303 K

$10^2 [\text{TEACC}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	1	2	3	4	5
$10^5 k_1$ (s ⁻¹)	7.02	6.98	6.99	6.94	7.01

Substrate dependence of the reaction rate

[TEACC] = 0.01 mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄] = 0.10 mol dm⁻³, Temp = 303 K

[BA] (mol dm ⁻³)	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.80	1.00
10^5 (s ⁻¹)	7.02	14.44	20.13	27.04	32.71

Dependence of the reaction rate on acidity

[BA] = 0.20 mol dm⁻³, [TEACC] = 0.01 mol dm⁻³, Temp = 303 K

[H ₂ SO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.25
$10^5 k_1$ (s ⁻¹)	3.45	7.02	10.81	14.68	18.22

Dependence of the reaction rate on solvent composition

[BA] = 0.20 mol dm⁻³, [TEACC] = 0.01 mol dm⁻³,

[H₂SO₄] = 0.10 mol dm⁻³, Temp = 303 K

DMF H ₂ O (% v/v)	100/0	95/5	90/10	85/15	80/20
D	37.6	39.7	41.8	43.9	46.1
$10^5 k_1$ (s ⁻¹)	7.02	4.68	3.89	3.09	2.63

Variation of rate constants with temperature

[BA] = 0.20 mol dm⁻³, [TEACC] = 0.01 mol dm⁻³,

[H₂SO₄] = 0.10 mol dm⁻³

Temp	303 K	308 K	313 K	318 K	323 K
$10^5 k_1$ (s ⁻¹)	7.02	9.79	14.48	21.45	28.77

1) that the reaction rate decreased with an increase in dielectric constant of the medium suggesting that the more polar solvents may require larger reaction time for the oxidation reactions. A plot of $\log k$ against inverse of dielectric constant is linear with a positive slope and implies the occurrence of an interaction between a dipole and a positive ion² and indicates the probable involvement of protonated chromium(vi) species, in the presence of an acid in the rate-determining step. There have been earlier reports of the involvement of such a chromium(vi) species in chromic acid oxidations³. The linear increase in the oxidation rate with acidity suggests the involvement of protonated chromium(vi) species in the rate-determining step.

Oxidation of benzyl alcohol has been carried out at five different temperatures, viz. 30, 35, 40, 45 and 50°. The rate of the reaction increases with increase in temperature (Table 1). The activation parameters were calculated from the linear plots of $\log k_2$ vs $1/T$. The thermodynamic parameters were calculated (ΔH , 49.08 kJ mol⁻¹; ΔS , -162.56 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹; ΔG , 98.34 kJ mol⁻¹). The high negative entropy value suggests that the solvent molecules are strongly oriented around the ions, thereby resulting in the loss of entropy⁴. This also accounts for lowering of the rate coefficients with increasing polarity of medium. Since all the reactions were performed under nitrogen, the possibility of induced polymerisation was tested. No polymerisation was seen with acrylonitrile. This indicates that one-electron oxidation was quite unlikely. In control experiments, the concentration of TEACC did not show any appreciable change.

The results point to hydride ion transfer in the rate-determining step of the TEACC oxidations. A hydrogen abstraction mechanism is unlikely in view of the failure to induce polymerisation of acrylonitrile. The hydride transfer

Scheme 1

may take place either directly (Scheme 1) or may involve the prior formation of a chromate ester (Scheme 2). The present data might also suggest, like the similar oxidations involving chromic acid³, chromate ester formation is the

Scheme 2

rate-determining step (Scheme 2) although Scheme 1 cannot be totally ruled out. It is also expected that the chromate intermediate will be better stabilised in the less polar medium and will enhance the oxidation rate, thus conforming to our observation.

Experimental

All chemicals used were reagent grade. Benzyl alcohol and dimethylformamide were purified and dried⁵ and their purity was checked. Sulphuric acid (E. Merck) and tetraethylammonium hydroxide (Fluka, 20% wt.) were used as such.

Tetraethylammonium chlorochromate : Anhydrous chromium(vi) oxide (5.0 g, 50 mmol) dissolved in 6 M HCl (9 ml, 55 mmol) was stirred at 0° for 5 min. To it a solution of tetraethylammonium hydroxide (20% in H₂O; 40 g, 55 mmol) was added over 10 min and the resulting orange yellow solid was washed and dried under reduced pressure for 3 h; Cr content was determined iodometrically (assay > 98%), yield, 91%, m.p. 225–26° (Found : N, 5.23. C₈H₂O₂CrNO₃Cl requires : N, 5.27%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 062, 1 043, 995, 938, 893, 774 and 429 cm⁻¹. The pH of TEACC after repeated crystallisation was 2.15 (30°).

For kinetic measurements, the reactions were performed under pseudo-first order conditions by maintaining a large excess of alcohol over TEACC at constant temperature (± 0.1 K) and the progress of the reaction was followed by iodometric estimation of unreacted chromium(vi) after quenching the reaction. All kinetic measurements were carried out in dimethylformamide in the presence of sulphuric acid. Computations of rate constants were made from the plot of $\log [\text{oxidant}]$ against time. The values reported are the mean of at least duplicate runs and are reproducible to within $\pm 5\%$. The reaction mixtures remained homogeneous in the solvent systems used.

Dielectric constants for the varying proportions of DMF-H₂O mixtures were estimated from the dielectric constants of the pure solvents⁶. A constant ionic strength could not be maintained owing to the nonaqueous nature of the reaction medium. However, the variation in ionic strength did not bring about any change⁷ in the oxidation of benzyl alcohol by chromium(vi) oxide in aqueous acetic acid medium. The catalysed reactions were studied at temperatures 303, 308, 313, 318 and 323 K (error limit ± 0.1 K). The activation parameters were evaluated by the standard procedure⁸ within allowable average error limit at 303 K.

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